

FUTURE CONTOURS OF GEORGIA'S ECONOMIC POLICY I.E. THE WAY FROM LIBERALISM TO CONSERVATISM

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Abstract

The enhancement of conservative attitudes in the USA and the leading European states is permanently reflected on the rest of the world. These changes also affect Georgia as a country integrated in the world economy, which has been trying to fulfil all the membership requirements after obtaining the status of the EU candidate state.

For Georgia, which is an ancient country with longstanding historical traditions, the turning of the liberal vector of development towards conservatism will be an undoubtedly positive event, because this enables the traditional nations with small population to preserve their identity, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, continue modernization of economy and implement innovations. The methodological basis for economic conservatism embraces stable development and traditional values, since stability yields perspective, which, in its turn, yields opportunities.

Based on the data of the Georgian National Statistics Office, the paper analyzes certain social-economic indicators in the country. These indicators will outline the contours of the new economic policy i.e. the way that Georgia has to pass from liberalism to modernized conservatism.

Keywords: globalization, innovation, liberalism, conservative economy, fiscal conservatism, inclusive economy.

Recently, the ideological vector has been shifted from liberalism to conservatism in the West. This process has become especially obvious after the victory of Donald Trump in the US presidential elections. This fact will change the system of opinions and values not only in politics but also in the economy worldwide.

The failure of liberalism was due to numerous factors. In our opinion, the key factors consisted in the globalization of economy and the idea of creating a new type of Man with new liberal values.

Instead of yielding new opportunities and prevention of economic crises, globalization led to serious economic problems worldwide. This was followed by decreased job opportunities, unemployment and large-scale migration. The reason for the above-mentioned was that powerful corporations easily penetrated into the markets of countries with comparatively weak economy. In most cases, by means of active investment policy, they restricted local industry and hampered innovative activities.

As for the development of a new type of Man, the idea turned out to be utopian, because it was impossible (despite great efforts) to alienate people from their historical roots. To quote great French philosopher and thinker Jean-Jacques Rousseau: "In some cases, there may be a discord between scientific progress and human values. The reason for such discord is that Man is not only part of nature, he also forms part of cultural environment." [4]

Conservative economy, often referred to as "fiscal conservatism", is an economic theory based on fiscal economy and financial responsibility. It implies low taxes and State expenditure, reduction of State debt, free trade, deregulation of economy, non-interference of the State in business and increased competitiveness of business entities." [7]

The ideological basis for economic conservatism is stable development and strengthening of traditional relations, since stability yields perspective, perspective yields opportunity, and all this enables activation of business and attraction of new investments.

Naturally, implementation of such large-scale political and economic changes will, above all, impact the USA, and, correspondingly, all the directions and key functions of the world's economic policy: distribution of resources within the State, macroeconomic stability and distribution of revenues.

Reasonable spending of resources is fundamental for conservative economy. Under the distribution of resources, conservatism implies the usage of material, human and financial resources in the process of reproduction. As a result of efficient distribution mechanisms, minimal expenditure of resources yields maximum result.

In conditions of crisis, macroeconomic stability is achieved by active involvement of the State in the management of the economy. The scale of interference depends on each concrete case of crisis. In general, conservators do not support the policy of interference in the economy and apply it only in special cases.

Distribution of revenue implies distribution of public wealth in the country, implemented by means of budget or social transfers allocated from the budget.

On the background of these revolutionary changes, a logical question arises with regard to Georgia: is the country ready for this kind of economic transformation?

In the past years, from the viewpoint of economic stability and sustainability, there have been impressive results: "In 2021-2023, the rate of increase in Georgia's GDP has comprised: in 2021 - 10.6%, in 2022 - 11.0% and in 2023- 7.8%. It should be noted that this increase

has been achieved in conditions of low inflation rate. In 2023, inflation comprised 2.5%, whereas in 2024, it comprised 1.1%.

The level of unemployment has shown stable reduction. "In 2022, the level of unemployment in Georgia comprised 17.2%, in 2023 -16.2%, and during nine months of 2024, it comprised 13.8%" [12].

Rational management of Georgia's economic potential, largely due to the desirable and safe environment for business and investments, ensured stable prices, low inflation, increased real revenue and welfare of the population. The increase in the economy has been largely contributed by "the foreign sector. Decreased monetary transaction from Russia and increased transactions from Europe and the USA prove the increasing economic and mental connection of Georgia's population with the West" [8].

As for the social indicators life standards, such as average salary and pension, there has been certain increase as well, in particular: „In the third quarter of 2024, average nominal monthly salary increased by 10.9%, whereas the average monthly salary of people hired in the business sector was increased by 9.1% in the same period.

According to the data of 2024, the average nominal salary in Georgia equals 724 USD. The average nominal salary in Azerbaijan in the same year equals 586 USD, whereas in Armenia the average nominal monthly salary in the same period equals 726 USD. With these indices, the countries of the Caucasus lag behind Russia and Turkey. In 2024, the average salary in Russia equalled 807 USD, while in Turkey it was approximately 1 000 USD.[10]

Among the neighbouring states, Georgia falls behind in the amount of pension, namely: the average pension in Georgia comprises about 124 USD, in Armenia it is 125 USD, whereas in Turkey and Russia the pension is above 200 USD" [11].

However, it should be mentioned that such direct comparison of salaries and pensions is not valid, because numerous factors must be taken into account, for instance, prices on customer goods, the purchasing power of the population, the level of employment, the demographic situation, mentality and so on.

In many fields of life, particularly in economics, conservatism does not exclude the opportunity of modernization. Macroeconomic stability forms a precondition for introducing innovations and reforms in the economy and adapting the latter to the country's cultural and historical identity.

Georgia and other small nations must be ready for the intermixture of tradition and innovation. This will enable the countries to preserve the system of traditional values, whereas innovative activities will add energy and experience.

Georgia has declared that its economic priority is inclusiveness. Numerous steps have been made in this regard and corresponding reforms have been implemented. Hence, a logical question: how can conservatism be combined with inclusive economy?

Modern conservatism is not a dogmatic theory. It succeeds in combining traditional values and reforms. Naturally, one of its priorities is optimal use of the

country's fiscal capacity. This, in its turn, will improve the welfare and living conditions of the population.

Conservatism does not oppose the idea of inclusion. Its essence is to establish a fair principle of distribution of wealth and increase the role and functions of the civil sector in the economic activity.

Fair economy is based on "several crucial principles that should be preserved for the purpose of achieving justice as an organic part of the logic of economic development. These principles are as follows: abstinence from political populism; subsequent economic reforms; order between the State, physical and legal entities in the distribution of public wealth [3].

In its nature, justice is an existential category. Yet, it is formed as a process of human relationship based on the tradition of historical, economic, ethnic and religious cohabitation. This brings synergy of conservatism and inclusion, enabling new job opportunities, overcoming of poverty, improvement of the educational system etc.

Implementation of the principles of conservative economy in Georgia will yield new prospects and attitudes in accordance with modern requirements and global challenges. Therefore, the epoch of conservatism will be quite tumultuous not only for Georgia but also for the entire civilized world.

In our opinion, due to the failure of liberalism, in the nearest decades conservatism will be a dominant political and economic ideology in the world. Thus, there will be an epoch of great innovations and transformations in numerous fields of social life.

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